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CLASSIFICATION OF PHONETIC TERMS IN ENGLISH, RUSSIAN AND UZBEK LANGUAGES

Annotation

The article deals with the classification of the phonetic terminology of the English, Russian and Uzbek languages. There are divided English phonetic terms into graphs, intonation and stress, vocalism and consonantism, and gives equivalents in other languages. Each of which contains a certain number of terms.

Key words: Term, phonetics, language, English, Uzbek, Russian, classification, graphics, intonation, vocalism, consonantism, group of terms.

ФОНЕТИК ТЕРМИНЛАРНИНГ ИНГЛИЗ, РУС ВА ЎЗБЕК ТИЛИДАГИ ТАСНИФИ

Аннотация

Мақолада инглиз, рус ва ўзбек тиллари фонетик терминологиясининг таснифи хақида сўз боради. Инглизча фонетик атамалар графикларга, интонация ва урғуга, вокализмга ва консонантизмга бўлиниб, бошқа тиллардаги эквивалентларни берилган. Уларнинг ҳар бири маълум миқдордаги атамаларни ўз ичига олади.

Калит сўзлар: Термин, фонетика, инглиз тили, ўзбек тили, рус тили, тасниф, график, интонация, вокализм, консонантизм, терминлар гуруҳи.

КЛАССИФИКАЦИЯ ФОНЕТИЧЕСКИХ ТЕРМИНОВ НА АНГЛИЙСКОМ, РУССКОМ И УЗБЕКСКОМ ЯЗЫКАХ

Аннотация

В статье рассматривается классификация фонетической терминологии английского, русского и узбекского языка. В нем разделяются английские фонетические термины на графики, интонации и ударения, вокализм и консонантизм и дано эквиваленты в других языках. Каждые из которых содержит определенное количество терминов.

Ключевые слова: Термин, фонетика, язык, английский язык, узбекский язык, русский язык, классификация, графика, интонация, вокализм, консонантизм, группа терминов.

Introduction. In world linguistics, attention to linguistic units - terms, which have their communicative-functional nature in various field contexts, lexicographic laws and translation issues related to them, has expanded the scope of studies in the field of terminology. The need for an adequate understanding of the theoretical concepts of modern Western linguistics and literary studies led to the demand for a scientific explanation of the linguistic status, intertextual and interdiscursive functionality of the terms of literary studies, which constituted a significant half of the science of English philology. After all, observation of terminological processes both linguistically and extra linguistically, determining their intertextual dynamic characteristics on the basis of a differential and integral approach creates an opportunity to theoretically evaluate the internal contradiction in the essence of field terms, the phenomenon of linguistic conceptualization related to human logic and thinking.

In world terminology, researches on the organization of phonetic terms and their manifestation as a verbal symbol of a specific concept in a specific context are being carried out within the framework of one language. The growing role of these terms in communicative processes, the complexity of the knowledge about the formation mechanisms, requires the implementation of a priority task such as their lexicographic, structural-content, formal and substantive interpretation in the context of translation. This, in turn, serves to observe the primary nominative principles characteristic of terms, to develop methods of analyzing their motivational character, to justify the influence of non-scientific factors on the linguistic form and lexicographic presentation of terms within the framework of modern linguistic consciousness.

Literature review. Terminology issues have always been the focus of scientists. Therefore, the terminological system of many languages, including English, has been studied to a certain extent. A number of studies have been conducted on general and specific terminology in English and other foreign languages and in Russian linguistics.

Issues of terminology in Uzbek linguistics N.T. Hotamov, M.E. Umarmho'jaev, H. Dadaboev, I. Kh. Sadykova, S.Kh. Nurmatova, O. Tursunova, P.P. Nishonov, O.S. Akhmedov. It is also studied in the works of such linguists as H.D. Paluanova, H. Kadyrbekova, H.V. Mirzakhmedova, S.T. Mustafaeva and D.I. Khodjaeva.

The field of terminology, like other areas of linguistics, is considered to be a field of science that deals with the most pressing problems in the language and tries to find answers to them from different angles and develop solutions. In all the works devoted to terminology, the compounds that mean certain concepts of one or another field, have a definition and perform mainly a nominative function are considered as terms. Terms are special names widely used by specialists in science, technology, art, and other fields of human activity. They, in turn, are divided into proterms, first terms and terminoids. Often, the concepts of term and nomenclature are used interchangeably. Therefore, it is necessary to react to the nomenclature in this place. Nomenclature (lat. nomenclatura "list") is the name of similar objects of science. If the term represents a general concept, the nomenclature represents a specific concept. For example, the names of types of educational institutions, teaching didactic equipment, etc. are nomenclature.

Research Methodology. The English language was formed from the dialects of various Germanic tribes that

inhabited in the 4th-5th centuries AD, as Jutland and the northwestern regions of Germany adjacent to the North Sea. The most important of these tribes are the Angles, Saxons and Jutes [4]. In ancient times, English was spoken over a vast territory. The number of speakers of this language was estimated at about one million. The first traces or phenomena of compiling a dictionary of phonetic terms of the English language coincide with the 9th century and the appearance of the work "Grammar of the English Language". This textbook is the first theoretical work written in English. In his work Grammar, Alfred used calquing extensively because it was one of the ways to borrow foreign words and laid the foundation for terminology and term formation of that time. A. Smirnitsky in his textbook "Old English" described in detail the phonetic structure of the Old English language. In this textbook, all phonetic terms that belong to one or another section of phonetics are indicated in detail.

Analysis and results. Based on these books, we have distributed all the phonetic terms of the English language into:

a) terms related to graphics, sound meanings of letters and writing. The Old English Latin alphabet differs in its composition from the usual one by the presence of additional characters, as well as literature as a permanent special character, which is used not sporadically only in individual spellings, but regularly along with other letters. For the ancient Germanic languages, the following three types of writing were known, which had more or less significant distribution: runic writing, Wulfilian (or Gothic) and Latin writing. The main terms and term combinations of this group are the following: letter- harf (буква), combination- tarkib (сочетание), sound-tovush (звук), runic letter- runik yozuvi (руническое письмо), sign-belgi (знак), latin alphabet- Lotin alifbosi (латинский алфавит), latin letter- Lotin harfi (латинское буква), capital letter – bosh harf (большая буква), lowercase letters- kichik harf (строчные буквы) which was worked out during the reign of Charlemagne (678-814) by the best scribes of the Franco state);

b) terms related to stress and intonation. In Old English, stressed syllables can be distinguished by stress of unequal strength. Thus, in general, three categories of syllables are defined: main stressed, secondary stressed and unstressed syllables. The main terms and term combinations of this group are as follows:

stress – urg'u (ударение), main stress- asosiy urg'u (главное ударение), secondary stress- ikkinchi darajali urg'u (второстепенное ударение), verbal stress – so'z urg'usi (словесное ударение), free stress- erkin urg'u (свободное ударение), unstressed, unaccented – urg'usiz (безударность), reduction – reduksiya (редукция), syllable – bo'g'in (слог), first syllable – birinchi bo'g'in (первый слог). It should be noted that in English term «main stress- - asosiy urg'u (главное ударение)» denoted by the sign ['], and the term «secondary stress- ikkinchi darajali urg'u (второстепенное ударение)» sign ;

c) terms related to vocalism. In English we find the following terms and phrases related to vocalism: vowel – unlil (гласный), simple vowels – oddiy unlilar (простые гласные), palatal – tanglay (палатальные), velar- tanglay orqasi (велярные), labialized – lablangan (лабиализованные), unlabialized – lablanmagan (нелабиализованные), rise- ko'tarilish (подъём), upper rise – yuqoriga ko'tarilgan (верхний подъём), middle rise – o'rta ko'tarilgan (средний подъём), lower rise – past ko'tarilgan (нижний подъём), diphthongs – diftong (дифтонги), short vowels – qisqa unlilar (краткие гласные), long vowels – cho'ziq unlilar (долгие гласные), o'zgarish – mutatsiya (мутация), fraction – kamaytirish (преломление), voiceless vowels - jarangsiz unlilar (безударные гласные), voiced vowels – jarangli unlilar (ударные гласные), palatal vowel - tanglay unlisi (палатальный гласный), velar vowel – bo'giz unlisi (велярный гласный).

d) terms related to consonantism. In English, the following phonetic terms and term combinations were used, which belonged to consonantism: consonant - undosh (согласный), bilabial – lab-lab (губно-губные), dental – tish (зубные), velar – tanglay orqa (велярные), palatal – tanglay (палатальные, нёбные), occlusive; obstruent – portlovchi (смычные), fricative – sirgaluvchi (фрикативные), nasal – burun (носовые), semivowel – yarim unli (полугласные), guttural – tomoq (гортанные), voiced – jarangli (звонкие), voiceless - jarangsiz (глухой), long – cho'ziq (двойные (долгие), short- qisqa (простые (краткие), palatal consonants – tanglay undoshlari (палатальные согласные), fricative consonants – sirgaluvchi undoshlar (фрикативные согласные), occlusive voiced consonants – portlovchi jarangli undoshlar (смычные звонкие согласные), fricative voiced consonants – sirgaluvchi jarangsiz undoshlar (звонкие фрикативные согласные), nasal consonants – burun undoshi (носовые согласные), guttural fricative consonants - xalqum undoshlari (гортанный фрикативный согласный). It should be noted that the term "labio-labial" turned into "labio-tooth" in the Middle English literary era.

In "Grammar" - Elfric in a series of detailed descriptions of parts of speech, the interpretation of the term «harf - letter (буква)» occupies a prominent place. In the section on interpretation «harf - letter (буквы)» phonetic terms that were not subjected to detailed study of that time became especially noticeable. The terms that appeared in the English language in the earliest period of its development (in the 9th century) include the words tongue and ridge (approximately 1% of the total number of lexemes and 25% of the total number of units from the period of the 9th century to the 13th century). Term tongue - til (язык) appeared in the Old English period in the writings of King Alfred (Gregory's Pastoral care, 897): An organ, possessed by a man and by most vertebrates, occupying the floor of the mouth, it is important in taking in and swallowing food, also as the principal organs of taste, and in man of articulate speech - Movable organ of humans and most vertebrates, located at the bottom of the oral cavity and necessary for swallowing food, important for taste perception, and in humans for speech formation [3].

Another phonetic term hard – qattiq (твердый) in the terminology hard palate – qattiq tanglay (твердое нёбо) dates from the ninth century. according to the X century. It should be noted that by the X century applies term teeth – tishlar (зубы) plural of tooth, whose origin dates back to the writings of King Alfred. This unit was borrowed without change from the common vocabulary, where it entered much earlier. Lexeme lungs – o'pka (легкие) appeared in the 11th century. in a meaning close to terminological, - "lungs (human respiratory organ)". By the 11th century also include 3 lexemes, including lungs, word, foot. The words word and foot in the indicated period were fixed in meanings close to terminological ones - word, as "a set of sounds that has a meaning" and foot as "foot in versification". The first word existed in the language before, but in the meaning of "saying, something said" (X century), and the second - in the direct meaning - "foot, lower part of the leg" [3].

The rest of the phonetic terms that were used in the specified period of the development of the English language are as follows:

-head (Head anterior (in man, upper) part of body, containing the mouth, sense organs, and brain; various transf. uses. OE. heafod "top of the body", also "upper end of slope", also "chief person, leader, ruler," from P. Gmc. khaubtuthan (cf. OS. hobid, ON. hofuð, OFris. haved, G. Haupt, Goth. haubip "head"), from PIE kauput-"head" (cf. Skr. kauput-, L. caput "head"), also "bowl" (as in skull). Modern spelling is c. 1420, representing what was then a long vowel (as in heat) [5];

-narrow (Narrow having little breadth OE; (dial) parsimonious, close; strict, close XIII; lacking in breadth of view or sympathy XVII. ME; OE. Nearu; c. OS. Naru narrow, Du.naar unpleasant; akin to G, narbe scar, lit., narrow mark) [5];

-open (Open adj. not shut, confined, or covered (with many fig. uses). (bef.900); (adj.) ME., OE; c. OS. opan (Du. open), OHG. offan (G. offen), ON. opinn, akin to up; (v) ME.

openen, OE. openian; c. OS. opanon (Du. openen), OHG. offanon (G. Offnen)) [5].

Conclusion/Recommendations.As we know, all the above terms are of Germanic origin, which were borrowed in the ancient period of the existence of the English language. Therefore, the influence of foreign languages such as Germanic and Greco-Latin was more visible in comparison with other languages.

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